

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

**Learning stories on insurance and financial
solutions**

Deliverable 4.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1 Learning stories on financial and insurance solutions

The EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change empowers European regions and local authorities to achieve climate resilience by 2030. In order to accelerate action to adapt to the consequences of climate change at regional and local level, novel financial and insurance solutions are essential. We need to overcome the following challenges in adaptation finance to accelerate investment and insurance of climate adaptation:

Provision of a comprehensive evidence base on the effectiveness of nature based solutions (by gathering data/by using standards/by monitoring and by reporting)

Reduction of transition costs by combining small scale projects into a portfolio of nature-based solutions that is more bankable

Larger involvement of the private sector in financing, possibly in combination with public co-funding to reduce risk

The enhancement of stakeholder engagement and bringing together buyers and sellers

Provide education and training for financing experts on adaptation and for adaptation experts on finance

In TransformAr, we are testing different financing mechanisms for adopting and scaling up climate adaptation investments. The TransformAr project, in support of the EU Mission on Adaptation, has demonstrated three financial solutions and has explored insurance solutions for adaptation. Each solution demonstrates a way to tackle a particular challenge in an integrated way. The different solutions and their contributions to overcoming barriers for adaptation finance are shortly described in Table 1. In the sections 1.1 to 1.4, each solutions is further explained in dept¹. Solutions 1.1-1.3 are specifically tested in one or two regions. By testing the solutions we identify lessons learned that can be taken into account when replicating the solutions in other regions. In 1.4, we describe the current lessons of insurance on adaptation over alle demo regions of TransformAr.

¹ In the learning stories of the cases, we will reflect on the challenges tackled, by indicating these with the icons above.

Figure 1. Location of the project countries, demo regions and financial and insurance solutions.

Table 1. Overview of the financial solutions tested in TransformAr and the challenges they tackled.

Challenges tackled

2.1 Discrete Choice Experiments, Finland and Norway – Testing new policy tools through behavioural economic experiments

Discrete choice experiments (DCE) create a better understanding of citizens' preferences for goods or policies that do not yet exist. They are key to informing both public and private policies on the acceptance of adaptive solutions. The DCE is used to improve understanding of the citizens' preferences for the stormwater management system upscaling in Finland and Norway by investigating the willingness of individual citizens to pay for and take action on stormwater management on their own properties. It integrates knowledge on citizens' preferences for climate adaptation to policy actions. Better understanding which segments of the population are willing to pay, as well as the trade-offs they are willing to make, is crucial for the development of targeted awareness campaigns and subsidy programs to incentivize private action.

2.2 Payment for ecosystem services, West Country (UK) – Trading platform for phosphate credits.

The phosphate credits, combined with green bonds is a methodology of setting up a market platform for non-market (common) goods using payment for ecosystem services (PES). The demonstrator in West Country, United Kingdom, is setting up a trading platform for phosphate credits. One of the challenges in the implementation is the evaluation of benefits. The valuation of the benefits is complex, potentially resulting in different outcomes, creating an inefficient trading market. As a result, proper monitoring is key to keeping proper track of the performance of measures and

correct valuation in the trading scheme. Furthermore, there is another challenge in the bankability related to the trading platform, i.e., the ability to attract parties prepared to pay for the required project costs of transformative adaptive solutions to address the impacts of climate change.

2.3 Adaptation Fund, Guadeloupe (FR) – Grants and loans for small and medium size businesses.

The adaptation fund represents a lifeline for communities vulnerable to climate change. These funds, distinct from traditional finance mechanisms, pool resources to address adaptation needs. Globally, initiatives like the [Green Climate Fund](#) provide financial support to developing nations, empowering them to confront climate threats head-on. Adaptation funds not only bridge public and private interests but also promote global solidarity in the fight against climate change. In TransformAr, the demonstrator in Guadeloupe is setting up a local adaptation fund.

2.4 Insurance, generally applicable – Covering damages

Attention to insurance schemes is important to address uncertainty in climate events. It is impossible to protect ourselves against the impact of climate events perfectly. Therefore, there is a need to provide insurance and protect us against the extreme risks that climate events can have. In TransformAr, demonstrators develop damage functions to assess the impact of climate risk. Damage functions can quantify the risk of climate events, e.g., flooding of a certain area or a specific building. Climate change might alter the current risk and lead to more damage. The insurance industry needs to know if and where damage is expected to increase in the upcoming decades to create healthy insurance schemes. In this way, the effectiveness of the other financial schemes is secured, and the risk of disruption is limited.

1.1 Discrete choice experiment in Finland and Norway

Testing new policy tools through behavioural economic experiments

Key learnings

- To adapt to the impacts of climate change, it is important that **both governments and citizens** act on stormwater management to **reduce vulnerabilities** to flood risk and pollution generated by extreme rainfall events.
- Through the TransformAr project, a **discrete choice experiment (DCE)** was conducted to estimate 2,013 Finnish and Norwegian citizens' **willingness to invest** in stormwater management measures on private properties; while also estimating the trade-offs they are willing to make while doing so. The results indicate **strong public acceptance** to both invest and take action.
- DCEs are a useful tool to **inform policy decisions** and discussions that require **behavioural change**. By building hypothetical scenarios through the DCE, one can anticipate the response of the target population (Imbens & Wooldridge, 2009).
- **Public participation** in policy discussions can result in more ambitious and transformative climate change planning and implementation. By simultaneously raising citizens' awareness, both implementation and behavioural change can be facilitated (EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, 2024).

Why should citizens act on adapting to impacts of climate change through stormwater management?

Stormwater management (SWM) has become a key policy response to lower urban susceptibility to **flood risk**, and resilience to runoff generated by heavy rainfall events (Henstra et al., 2020). SWM systems imitate natural features allowing for water drainage in a quick and efficient way. SWM also improves **water quality** because of a reduction in runoff pollutants flowing into local streams, rivers, and lakes, while also benefiting biodiversity.

In the event of extreme weather events, local stormwater networks are currently overloaded. The reason for this overload is that local drainage networks are not designed for the extent of extreme rainfall that is currently occurring as a result of climate change (TransformAr, 2022). **Restricted resources** of local governments to effectively address and adapt to the growing risks and impacts of climate change, highlight the significance of citizens' adaptation actions (Brink & Wamsler, 2019). By recognising the importance of their role, **private citizens can contribute** to creating a more resilient society by installing stormwater management systems on their properties themselves. Such SWM measures include those referred to as 'green infrastructure', including **rain gardens, permeable surfaces, green ditches, green walls, and green roofs**, and 'grey infrastructure', such as **stormwater chambers, sump pumps, pipes**, and the redirection of **drainpipes**. An important objective for sustainable cities is encouraging citizens to invest in the SWM measures that fit their needs best.

Citizens' benefits of private SWM measures include, among others: **personal safety** - SWM measures can help protect homes from damage caused by flooding; **economic benefits**: investing in resilient infrastructure can prevent costly damage from climate-related events, but also help conserve water resources through rainwater harvesting; **health and ecosystem benefits** thanks to improved local water quality. In certain cases, SWM measures, in particular green infrastructure, can improve **aesthetics** and **market value of households**, while at the same time providing habitats for **local biodiversity** (in the case of green roofs for instance).

About the regions

Lappeenranta (61-06°N, 28-19 °E) is a Finnish city covering an area of 1,724 km² situated in the region of 'South Karelia' (aka. Etelä-Karjala) on the south-eastern frontier of Finland, 30 kilometres away from the Russian border. The city is located on the shores of Lake Saimaa, which is the largest lake in Finland. Gjøvik (60.7954° N, 10.6916° E) is a Norwegian city located in inland Norway on the shores of lake Mjøsa, which is Norway's largest lake. Gjøvik is a modern small city in growth with 30.000 inhabitants. In the TransformAr project, Gjøvik is Lappeenranta's solution replicator.

Figure 3. Location of Lappeenranta in Finland

Climate Hazards

Increased rainfall, extreme weather events, urban flooding, flooding of waterways, and contaminants and nutrients decreasing water quality in local water bodies.

Sector: Urban planning and water management

Key system

Urban runoff system (stormwater management), including nature-based solutions and green infrastructure, as well as grey infrastructure.

Figure 3. Photo of Gjøvik (with similar landscapes to Lappeenranta)

How TransformAr investigated citizens' willingness to invest in stormwater management infrastructure on their private properties

Hypothetical scenario

All respondents were presented with the following hypothetical scenario: "You are considering purchasing one of the below stormwater management measures for your private property to capture increased rainfall and stormwater.² You own a detached 120 m² house with a garden."

Costs and benefits of stormwater measures to be considered by respondents

Once the respondents were presented with information on the stormwater management measures, they were asked to

Figure 4. Hypothetical property owned by all respondents taking part in DCE, showing possible SWM measures that they could choose to install.

² Detailed information was provided on the stormwater management measures presented in the hypothetical scenario, including a green roof, green wall, rain tank, stormwater chamber, permeable surface, rain garden, and sump pump.

choose their preferred measure based on costs and benefits – or characteristics of the measure - shown in Table 2. The trade-offs that respondents needed to make related to the level of (1) **reduced risk of damage** to their house, (2) **reduced stormwater run-off and pollution**, (3) **improved aesthetics** of the property and community (4) frequency of **maintenance** required, and 5) the **price**. The specific measure was not specified, but all the options did represent a type of SWM measure indirectly. The prices provided were for a detached 120 m² house with a garden as was presented in the hypothetical scenario.

Table 2. Characteristics of SWM measures to be considered by respondents and their possible costs and benefits (levels)

		<u>Definition</u>	<u>Levels to choose from</u>
	Reduced risk of damage to the house	By installing effective stormwater management measures on your property, you reduce the risk of flooding and minimise potential damage caused by excessive rainfall compared to what may occur in its present condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less risk of damage - 50 % less risk of damage - 25 % less risk of damage • No reduction in risk of damage (same as now)
	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Stormwater runoff is the water that flows over the surface when it rains or when snow and ice melt. Instead of soaking into the ground, this water runs off over streets, parking lots, and rooftops, picking up pollutants (like oil, chemicals, sediments and debris). Effective stormwater management will reduce the stormwater runoff from your property, including pollutants, flowing into local water bodies, thus ensuring local water quality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less run-off pollutants - 50 % less run-off pollutants - 25 % less run-off pollutants • No reduction in run-off pollutants (same as now)
	Improved aesthetics of the property and community	The stormwater measure can beautify your property and the local community (or not).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No (same as now)
	Frequency of maintenance required	The frequency at which you will have to take action to maintain the stormwater management measure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once every 2 months • Once every 6 months • Once a year • Once every 2 years
	Price (investment cost)	The price to pay to install the stormwater management measure on your property.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 000 KR/10 000 EUR • 40 000 KR/4 000 EUR • 10 000 KR/1 000 EUR • 5000 KR/500 EUR

Example of a choice card presented to respondents

Respondents were given the option to choose a SWM measure to install on their hypothetical private property 6 independent times. They were given 3 options (option A, option B, or Option C, the latter of which referred to the opt-out choice and installing no new SWM measure). An example of the choice card which is made up of differing levels of the 5 characteristics presented in Table 2, is shown in Table 3 .

Table 3. Example of 1 of 6 choice scenarios (choice cards) presented to all respondents

	Reduced risk of damage to the house	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Improvement of aesthetics of the property and community	Frequency of maintenance required	Price (investment cost)
A	 5000 KR				
B	 100 000 KR				
C	No new stormwater management measure				

Overall results of the TransformAr DCE on willingness to invest in SMW in Finland and Norway

Out of the 1,013 respondents in Finland, and 1000 respondents in Norway, a representative sample of the population was surveyed in terms of age, gender, income, and education. Pre-and post-experimental questions included in the questionnaire allowed us to investigate whether living situation has an impact on willingness to invest in SWM - for instance whether they currently live in an apartment or house, whether they rent or own, or past experiences such as whether their property has previously been affected by floods, or whether their neighbourhood had been affected by floods could make an impact on respondents' choices.

In both Norway and Finland, respondents indicated a **clear positive preference towards taking personal action and investing in SWM** as opposed to opting-out and not installing any new stormwater management measure. Respondents showed a positive preference for installing the measures that ensured a **higher reduction in risk of damage** to their house, those that ensured a **higher reduction in stormwater runoff and pollution**, and those that improved the **aesthetics** of the property and local community. Respondents showed a **negative preference towards measures that had a higher price and frequency of maintenance** required.

Nonetheless, certain segments of our target group showed distinct preferences – for instance, **younger respondents** were more positive towards taking action and showed a higher willingness to invest in SWM, as did those with **higher incomes, education**, respondents whose **properties had a high market value**, and those that had **previously experienced floods** (both on their property as well as in their neighbourhood). Respondents who **owned** their properties showed a higher affinity towards measures that improved aesthetics of their household.

Respondents' overall willingness to pay to install a SWM, depending on its characteristics and associated costs and benefits related to reduced risk of damage to house and stormwater runoff and pollution, are shown below (one-off investment cost):

Reduced risk of damage to the house

If 25% less risk of damage: €1580 (Norway) - €3083 (Finland)

If 50% less risk of damage: €2040 (Norway) - €4209 (Finland)

If 75% less risk of damage: € 2710 (Norway) - €4820 (Finland)

Reduced stormwater runoff and pollution

If 25% less runoff pollutants: € 1340 (Norway) - € 1592 (Finland)

50% less runoff pollutants: € 4240 (Norway) - € 3737 (Finland)

75% less runoff pollutants: € 3640 (Norway) - € 3143 (Finland)

After completing the DCE, respondents were also asked which stormwater management measure(s) they had in mind to install on their private properties. They could choose more than one. As shown in the table below, both green and grey infrastructure was considered by respondents. The percentage illustrates the sample of the respondents that indicated that they wished to install the given measure on their private property.

Table 4. SWM measures respondents had in mind to install on private properties in DCE

SWM respondents had in mind to install on private properties during DCE	Finland	Norway
Permeable surface (e.g. replace asphalt in driveway with gravel or paving stones)	33 %	31 %
Rain garden	18 %	25 %
Green ditch	9 %	22 %
Green wall	9 %	16 %
Stormwater chamber	9 %	11 %
Sump pump	22 %	15 %
Rain tank	7 %	17 %
Redirecting the drainpipe	35 %	25 %
Green roof	24 %	8 %
None of above	21 %	21 %

Why understanding citizens' willingness to take action on climate change adaptation is important, and how DCEs can be used for this purpose

DCEs are a useful tool to **inform policy decisions** and discussions that require **behavioural change**. By building hypothetical scenarios through the DCE, one can anticipate the response of the target population (Imbens & Wooldridge, 2009). When also including the public in policy reflections, one can better **understand acceptance for future action**, which groups of the population are more **willing to engage**, and what is needed to **encourage** other groups of the population to ensure more ambitious and transformative climate change planning and implementation. By raising citizens' awareness in addition,

implementation of action, including behavioural change can be facilitated. TransformAr's study on the willingness to invest in stormwater management measures in Finland and Norway illustrates an encouraging learning story showing **willingness on behalf of the general population to both invest and act on climate change adaptation**. Local authorities can make use of this information to make data-driven decisions when developing policies, including stormwater fees and subsidies, but also to raise awareness on options and opportunities available to private citizens. Such public participation is key to ensure **transparency and accountability** in governance on climate change adaptation (EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, 2024). Further, by being proactive about climate change adaptation, citizens can play a critical role in creating a more resilient future for themselves and their communities.

References D1.1 Choice experiment in Finland and Norway

Brink, E., & Wamsler, C. (2019). Citizen engagement in climate adaptation surveyed: The role of values, worldviews, gender and place. Journal of cleaner production, 209, 1342-1353.

EU Missions Adaptation to Climate Change. Do it yourself (DIY) manual for mobilising and engaging stakeholders and citizens in climate change adaptation planning and implementation

Henstra, D., Thistlethwaite, J., & Vanhooren, S. (2020). The governance of climate change adaptation: stormwater management policy and practice. Journal of environmental planning and management, 63(6), 1077-1096.

Imbens, G. W., & Wooldridge, J. M. (2009). Recent developments in the econometrics of program evaluation. Journal of economic literature, 47(1), 5-86.

TransformAr: Khamis, R.; Lenoir, L.; Simonet, S., Tranchant, M. (2022) Catalogue tool to identify best available solutions. TransformAr Deliverable 3.2, H2020 grant no. 101036683

TransformAr: Khamis, R; Simonet, S. Varis, S., Roch, J; Couldrick, L. et al. (2022) Stakeholder matrix and IEs Baseline Profiles. TransformAr Deliverable 1.2, H2020 grant no. 101036683

1.2 Payment for ecosystem services in West Country Region, UK

A trading platform for phosphate credits

Key learnings

- Achieving private sector investments: **Policy** interventions can help to **leverage** greater **private** sector investment into climate adaptation
- **Flexible** financing models have multiple benefits: Flexible nutrient credit models support mutually beneficial relationships between all key parties, whilst delivering for the environment
- Organisations which act as '**ethical brokers**' are **critical** to achieving these win-wins
- **Online platforms support stakeholder involvement** and capacity building: Innovative platforms including virtual natural capital marketplaces help to unite relevant parties, building new relationships and networks that support additional development of new projects and opportunities

About the region

The Westcountry is one of the UK's primary agricultural regions and contains a wide variety of protected habitats. The River Axe, the River Camel and the Somerset Levels are designated Sites of Special Scientific Interest and Special Areas of Conservation. These designations mean that each site contains rare species of flora and fauna and are protected under the Conservation of Habitats and Species Regulations.

Climate Hazards

Sea Level Rise, Storms, Extreme Temperatures, Flooding, Droughts

Sector

Financial, Agriculture, Water Management

Key system

Ecosystem and Nature Based Solutions, Water Management, Land-use and Food systems, Local Economic System Rivers

Climate threats

Due to the intensity of regional livestock farming, catchments in the Westcountry region are vulnerable to **nutrient pollution**: a vulnerability that is intensified by climate change. Hotter, drier summers, combined with **soil compaction**, lead to **flooding** events, as the soils are incapable of absorbing rainwater at a fast enough rate. Worsening **extreme precipitation** causes greater runoff in winter months, meaning nutrients enter waterways causing **eutrophication** and **biodiversity loss**.

Nutrient Pollution & Climate Change

As a result of nutrient pollution, which is aggravated by climate change, data shows that two-thirds of UK’s rivers failed to meet the targets of the **Water Framework Directive** ecological health test. This is due to **agricultural pollution** from fertilizer inputs or livestock husbandry, with more than half of the rivers failing the test due to activities attributed to the water industry. In addition, only 15% of rivers achieved ‘good’ ecological status. The problem is exacerbated by **insufficient investment** in maintaining water company infrastructure and a lack of central funding for water quality improvement and climate change adaptation measures. Green finance solutions are essential to secure greater funding for enhancing water quality.

Figure 5. 2022 data showing pollution source apportionment for poor water quality in England's rivers.

Taking Action: Nutrient Neutrality

In March 2022, the UK introduced Nutrient Neutrality legislation to combat water quality issues. Following the Dutch Nitrogen Case, ruling that nutrient loading into internationally important protected sites must be limited the UK legislation requires developers to **offset excess nutrients**. The legislation requires new dwellings not to add burden to sewage systems and wastewater treatment plants. In the Netherlands, this has led to the development of nitrogen permits. Meanwhile, in the UK, planning permission in Sites of Special Scientific Interest and Special Areas of Conservation has been suspended until developers obtain **phosphate credit purchase agreements**, proving they offset the additional projected nutrient load from their housing projects. To fulfil the demands of this new legislation, nutrient credits and pilot marketplaces began appearing in affected areas across the UK.

Measures to address diffuse agricultural pollution

In order to tackle diffuse agricultural pollution, and meet the demands of new nutrient neutrality legislation, the Westcountry Rivers Trust is (1) delivering Nature Based Solutions for **nutrient mitigation**, including riparian buffer strips, ponds and scrapes, and, (2) testing emerging **ecosystem service markets**

as a mechanism to pay landowners to reinstate these solutions along river corridors. The **co-benefits** of these interventions, including flood mitigation, drought resilience, improved water quality and larger habitats for native species, **enable the cross-sectoral climate adaptation** identified through the TransformAr stakeholder workshops.

Figure 6. Diagram demonstrating how buffer strips protect rivers from agricultural impacts.

Nature-Based Solutions for Phosphorous Mitigation

The Westcountry Rivers Trust is working with **landowners** to develop riparian buffer strips, restore wetlands and establish scrapes and ephemeral ponds along river corridors. Other measures, such as wetland restoration, floodplain reconnection, and the establishment of ephemeral ponds and scrapes, help mitigate nutrient pollution. Westcountry Rivers Trust farm advisors worked with farmers and landowners to generate bespoke plans for each site. These interventions will perform the ecosystem services which are ultimately sold as nutrient credits.

Delivery Partnerships & Natural Capital

The Westcountry Rivers Trust operates as a ‘Delivery Partner’ for the [North Devon Biosphere’s Natural Capital Marketplace](#), and Cornwall Council’s Local Investment in Natural Capital [Platform](#). Whilst chiefly working as **edit marketplaces**, these platforms also **host a virtual consortium**, uniting relevant parties to achieve more strategic, innovative approaches to **financing conservation efforts**. Relationships between parties within nutrient credit trading models are often complex.

An ideal nutrient credit trading model comprises... In reality, many partners may wear many hats and have various roles. For example, farmers/non-farming landowners may be unable to invest initial capital and undertake necessary work to develop credits on their land. As a delivery partner associated with the Natural Capital Marketplace and Local Investment in Natural Capital, the platform operators can facilitate **communication** and begin negotiations between possible **investors, farmers** and delivery **partners** like the Westcountry Rivers Trust, who may be able to deliver the practical work through existing project funding.

Next Steps

The Westcountry Rivers Trust has applied to become a Responsible Body. This means the trust has the **legal power to set up conservation covenants with landowners**, ensuring that natural landscape features are protected. This innovative legal mechanism strengthens confidence in natural capital, as it creates legal accountability for landowners to maintain ecosystem service provision. Investors can therefore confidently make up-front credit payments to farmers/landowners, helping to bridge the gap between subsidy funding and PES models. Becoming a responsible body will further enable the Westcountry Rivers Trust to **accelerate the uptake of green financing opportunities in the Westcountry region**.

Summary

In order to tackle nutrient pollution aggravating the effects of climate change, the Westcountry Rivers Trust has implemented Nature Based Solutions for phosphorous mitigation and tested emerging ecosystem service markets. The trust is a delivery partner and ethical broker, working to establish trading models that work well in the Westcountry region. Joining multi-sector natural capital platforms has highlighted the value of these organisations for accelerating the uptake of green finance for nutrient mitigation and climate adaptation in the region. It has also demonstrated how public funding can complement private sector investment, highlighting how policy interventions can help to leverage greater private sector investment for climate adaptation. The example shows that local authorities can create a robust credit allocation policy.

Further information

- [The river trust](#)
- [The Nitrogen crisis in The Netherlands](#)
- [Nutrient neutrality and housing development in the UK](#)

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1.3 Adaptation fund in Guadeloupe, France

Grants and loans for small and medium size businesses

By its geographical position and its biophysical characteristics, Guadeloupe is subject to almost all existing **natural disasters**, climate related or not (floods, drought, forest fires, storms and hurricanes, land movement, earthquake, volcano eruption). As part of the Caribbean region, Guadeloupe islands are particularly impacted by climate change yet (1) national and local fundings mostly **target post disaster recovery actions** or **mitigation**, (2) actions of local institutions are **not coordinated** to meet the needs in terms of **adaptation** (3) **private sector is difficult** to bring on board. **Agriculture** and **tourism**, the main sectors of the archipelago's economy, are particularly vulnerable to the aforementioned climate threats. The climate hazards are more frequent and more intense on these sectors (particularly floods, droughts and hurricanes). They are generating other threats to the agriculture and the tourism sectors like coastal erosion, land salinization, sargassum seaweed invasion, heat waves etc.

Key learnings

- **Funding:** Accelerate the deployment of innovative and concrete climate change adaptation projects by providing fundings available locally
- **Cofinancing:** Meet the interests of both public and private sectors by making projects bankable and facilitating administrative procedures (due diligence checking, grant allocation)
- **Engagement:** Ensure relevant governance and a relevant use of the financial mechanism by involving local stakeholders from the conception of the fund (governance, eligibility criteria...) to its implementation.
- **Collaboration:** Ensure smart financing by aligning all parties' interests and harmonizing their administrative-legal procedures.

About the region

Guadeloupe is a French region of 1628 km² located in the Caribbean Sea.

388 000 inhabitants live in the 6 main islands composing the archipelago

Climate Hazards

Hurricanes, Droughts, Floods, Rising temperature, Coastal erosion.

Sector

Agriculture and Tourism

Figure 7. Location of Guadeloupe in the Caribbean

Limited access to funding

French government fundings to cope with climate change are mostly targeting mitigation while there is an urgent need for EU outermost regions to adapt to immediate effects of climate change. More and more, the EU is supporting good practices exchanges such as the Program of exchanges in the EU outermost regions.

In addition, the **French European Outermost Regions** are known to **struggle** in raising European **fundings**. This led the European Commission, the OECD and the Ministry of French Oversea Territories to launch programmes to “Promote the mobilization of direct and indirect EU management programs in the outermost regions”. Several factors are already pointed out by this ongoing program like **communication** on the financing opportunities, **language** barrier and **local staff** training in fund raising.

Although Guadeloupe is located in the Caribbean Sea, as a French region, it cannot benefit from international funding dedicated to developing countries like its neighbours.

The 8 ambitions behind local fundings

The **Local Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe (FLAG)** is the most advanced, adaptation focused, financial mechanism in France. The set up of the FLAG is a key to:

- **Unlock** and reorientate budgetary resources for adaptation
- **Support** the realization of innovative adaptation solutions locally
- **Encourage** the development of local strategic policies on adaptation
- **Bridge** the gap between public needs and private interests in climate adaptation
- **Go further** than existing post-disaster compensation and regulatory aids
- **Reconsider** the scope of fundings to meet local needs more precisely
- **Create** partnerships for more synergies between the different local stakeholders
- **Develop** financial engineering to manage simultaneously diversified sources of financing

Setting a Local Adaptation Fund in a European Outermost Region

“We wanted to develop a Local Adaptation Fund through a collaborative approach to get as close as possible to all parties needs and interests, from the beneficiaries to the investors. We attempted to target the biggest challenges: making projects bankable, setting a political framework for adaptation, bringing human resources support locally.”

Marie-Edith Vincennes, Project Manager at ADEME Guadeloupe

Phase 1. Feasibility study for the financial mechanism

The experiment of setting up a FLAG is organized in two phases. ADEME has first worked on a feasibility study through desk review and field work for two years. Around 30 interviews, 2 surveys, 7 workshops have been conducted with the ambition of:

- Understanding climate finance : state of the art on climate finance, **benchmarking** of regional and **local adaptation fund worldwide**;
- Understanding the territory of experimentation: **mapping of local investors**, relevant local **stakeholders**, mapping of existing budget lines dedicated to climate change action, mapping of financial instruments compatible locally;
- **Comparing** the desk review to concrete implementation of climate finance on the ground;
- **Understanding** the needs of investors and beneficiaries to orientate fundings;

- Establish **prerequisites** and mandatory implementation conditions to set up the Fund (financial and human resources needed, permission and agreements needed);
- Bringing the gap between setting up of a FLAG and local policies priorities in the targeted sectors;
- Establishing and assessing **scenarios** for the governance of the FLAG.

Phase 2. Testing of the financial mechanism

The second phase of the setting of a local adaptation fund consists in the **testing** of the financial mechanisms with local stakeholders targeted in the Feasibility Study (investors, facilitators, beneficiaries).

Creation of a Technical and Financial Committee

The Committee with around 15 members has been set by ADEME in June 2023. Earlier, during a workshop in April 2023 participants were invited to identify relevant technical and financial partners. Adjustment had to be made after discussions and negotiations with each partner. For example :

Some partners like the French Development Agency where initially identified as financial partners however, they could only financed very large projects (over 500 000 euros), not corresponding to the local targets of the experiment.

Some partners joined later and has to fit in established cofinancial plans.

The Committee is gathering 15 technical and 7 financial partners, mostly from the public sector.

Launch of a project call

As part of the call for projects, beneficiaries were invited to propose solutions to adapt to one or more of these climatic hazards: Hurricanes, Floods, High temperatures, Droughts, Coastal erosion.

The projects proposals had to fall into one or more of the categories of climate change adaptation solutions mentioned below:

1. Governance: projects aimed at putting in place policies, regulations and coordination mechanisms to facilitate adaptation to climate change.
2. Nature-Based Adaptation Solutions: projects using ecosystems and their services to strengthen climate resilience.
3. Technology: projects exploiting technological or technical innovations to facilitate adaptation to climate change.

4. Behavior change: projects encouraging the adoption of sustainable individual and collective practices in order to promote lifestyles adapted to climate change.

Within each category differ types of projects can be selected. Examples are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Different types of projects possible for applying to the adaptation fund

Types of project	Examples
Studies	Climate risk analysis, vulnerability diagnostics, feasibility study, adaptation action plans...
Research & Innovation	Climate modelling, new practices, new organisation process...
Investment	Equipment installation, development of practices and methods, experiments...
Behavior change	Training programs, awareness campaign, engineering dedicated to adaptation within local authorities bodies or associations...

Criteria of evaluation

The projects were evaluated on several criteria that have been shared in the terms of reference of the project call. The evaluators were members of the Technical and Financial Committee.

1st group of criteria: Relevance of the project/50

- *The project is relevant with regard to the objectives of the AAP, the scientific and technical quality of the proposal / 20*
- *The project contributes to improving adaptation to climate change in Guadeloupe (Climate justification of the project) / 20*
- *The project is innovative and experimental (transformational adaptation) or a classic project integrating adaptation to climate change (adjustment) / 10*

2nd group of criteria: Project viability / 30

- *The adequacy of resources (human and financial) with the ambitions of the project / 10*
- *The quality of the team's organization /4*
- *A realistic and achievable work plan that includes the type of technical assistance needed for implementation /6*
- *The project is sustainable and replicable in Guadeloupe /10*

3rd group of criteria: Unifying aspect of the project / 20

- *The project is a collective approach (cooperation, pooling, capitalization, exchanges) / 4*
- *The project is part of a necessary, existing or emerging dynamic in Guadeloupe / 8*
- *The project is adapted to the characteristics of the Guadeloupean territory / 6*
- *The project contributes to the economy, livelihoods or important services of Guadeloupe /2*

Projects cannot exceed 2 years of implementation.

The challenges of setting a multi-actor financial mechanism

✓ **6 projects** for a total of **1 240 000 euros** have been selected through the project call. Their financial plan is displayed in Table 6. A brief description of the project is provided below:

- The “Porc Créole” project aims to answer local needs in porc by operating **genetic selection of creole pig**, a breed naturally adapted to tropical climate and thus rising temperature
- The “PLUVARIDE” project aims to enhance agricultural resilience in Guadeloupe by setting **food control reservoirs**, channels for drainage and implementing agroecological and agroforestry practices to address flooding and drought. It involves creating a smart-climate pilot farm to train local farmers
- The “Optisystemes” project aims to enhance Guadeloupe's agricultural sector by integrating **digital tools and data analysis** to address climate change challenges. By installing weather stations, soil and water sensors, and developing an online platform for data management, the initiative will improve water use efficiency, support informed decision-making, and foster adaptation to climate impacts.
- The “MétéEAU Nappes” project aims to enhance **groundwater resource** management by providing **real-time and predictive data on water levels**. This initiative is crucial for adapting to climate change, as it will improve drought preparedness and sustainable water use in the region's agriculture by offering early warnings systems.
- The project “RESAFOR” aims to promote **agroforestry for vanilla production** in Guadeloupe. By establishing guidelines and providing **good practices monitoring**, the initiative seeks to improve soil health, reduce environmental impact, and increase resilience to climate-related challenges, such as droughts, hurricanes and floods, while ensuring economic viability for local farmers.
- The “DRAINAGE” project aims to improve resilience and **efficiency in water use**, ensuring better adaptation to extreme weather conditions and sustainable water resource management by creating a body with a shared governance between public and private sectors. Support will also be provided to farmers with innovative water solutions.

Table 6. Visual of the financial plan of the adaptation fund

Project number	23GAD0109	23GAD0106	23GAD0105	23GAD0094	23GAD0093	23GAD0100	TOTAL
Project acronym	DRAINAGE	PORC CREOLE	PLURAVIDE	OPTISYSTEMES	METEO'NAPPES	RESAFOR	
Project leader	IT2 - Institut Technique Tropical	JDC - Les Jardins de Chayah	JDC - Les Jardins de Chayah	MYDITEK	BRGM - Geological and Mining Research Office	APAGWA-Association De Promotion De L'agriculture Et Du Developpement Rural En Guadeloupe	
Project Total Cost	173 960,50 €	138 400,00 €	228 495,00 €	475 945,00 €	95 999,24 €	127 252,00 €	1 240 051,74 €
Total Cost of Public Aid	139 191,19 €	97 520,00 €	159 950,00 €	285 697,80 €	76 000,00 €	121 774,00 €	880 132,99 €
Total Cost (including private aid)	139 191,19 €	122 520,00 €	184 950,00 €	385 698,00 €		121 774,00 €	954 133,19 €
ADEME	65 191,19 €	56 000,00 €	129 150,00 €	115 697,80 €		59 820,44 €	425 859,43 €
Regional Council	35 000,00 €	41 520,00 €		120 000,00 €			196 520,00 €
Bank of the territories			30 800,00 €	50 000,00 €	41 000,00 €	28 200,00 €	150 000,00 €
Departmental Council	14 000,00 €					35 000,00 €	49 000,00 €
Water Office	25 000,00 €			35 000,00 €	35 000,00 €		95 000,00 €
BRED Bank		TBD	TBD				
Crédit Agricole Bank				100 000,00 €			100 000,00 €

- ☑ **7 public and private local investors** agreed to cofinance these 6 projects up to **880 000 euros**.

The selected projects are financed by a minimum of 2 investors and a maximum of 4. Except the Bank of the Territories who delegates its funds to Ademe, all investors are in charge of the instruction and the monitoring of the projects they invested in. However, Ademe is in charge of the overall coordination of the 6 projects and therefore does most of the monitoring to keep the Committee members updated.

Instruction time, particularly in the public sector has been challenging. All the investors have different legal and administrative processes for instruction and cofinancing and some lack of engineering dedicated to projects instruction, slowing down the design of cofinancing plans. In total, one year was necessary to gather all investors and have official letters and agreements on their definitive contributions.

Another challenge was to bring on board the **private sector to finance adaptation projects**. The private banks were not often participating to the Committee activities. They were only interested in investment projects carried by businesses (Small and Medium Enterprises for our experimentation in Guadeloupe).

ADEME thus encouraged the **development of investment plans** and arguments by the enterprises: proof of the enterprise financial health, brochures presenting their projects with expected revenues, financing plans showing that strong public institutions trust these projects (public institutions funding served as a leverage)... In short, while public institutions selected the projects to be financed via the Committee, private banks selected the projects bilaterally by dealing directly with the beneficiaries.

The enterprises managed to obtain loans and contracts for the rent of equipment (leasing) from two local banks.

The governance of the Local Adaptation Fund in a European Outermost Region

Several options were studied for the governance of the FLAG. Among them, three, described below, appear to be more relevant:

1. A common budget line is managed by an independent entity created specifically for the Local Adaptation Fund
2. A common budget line dedicated to the Local Adaptation Fund is managed by an existing entity (coordinator)
3. Budget lines dedicated to the Local Adaptation Fund are managed independently by investors. An existing entity coordinates the selection process.

The specifics of all three options are shown in Table 7.

In order to test the mechanism in Guadeloupe demonstrator, ADEME launched a project call with a hybrid governance combining option 2 and 3.

The French Ecological Transition Agency (ADEME) of Guadeloupe is the existing entity named by the local stakeholders to coordinate the Fund. Some investors chose to delegate an envelope to ADEME before the launch of the project call (option 2), others financed independently the projects they were interested in after the project call (option 3).

Table 7. Three main options that were considered as governance framework for the adaptation fund.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Governance	<p>A charter of commitment is signed by investors</p> <p>A Projects Selection Committee is created with technical officers / experts from relevant local institutions</p> <p>Yearly, investors delegate funds to the entity in charge of the instruction and the financing of the selected projects</p>	<p>The entity coordinating the initiative meet officially with the identified technical partners and investors and see how they are willing to contribute (maximum amount of financing and conditions).</p> <p>Bilateral and / or multilateral agreements are signed by investors to take into account each investor's conditions.</p> <p>A Technical Committee is created to establish criterias of eligibility according to the technical relevance of the projects and conditions of the investors.</p> <p>An Investors Committee is created and gather after the Technical Committee has shorlisted the projects.</p>	<p>The entity coordinating the initiative meet officially with the identified technical partners and investors and see how they are willing to contribute (maximum amount of financing and conditions).</p> <p>The entity coordinating the initiative shortlist projects and official letters of demands for cofinancing are sent to the investors with previsional cofinancing plans.</p> <p>The stakeholders (local technical partners and investors) establish criterias of eligibility for the projects.</p>
Acces to beneficiaries	<p>More accessible to beneficiaries who only have to submit their project to one entity and have one contract</p> <p>The entity is non-political thus more impartial</p>	<p>More accessible to beneficiaries who only have to submit their project to one entity and have one contract.</p> <p>A Technical Committee shortlists the projects before the investors final decision thus the process is more impartial.</p>	<p>This option is not facilitating beneficiaries who have to submit their project to the different investors, delays of projects' instruction varies according to the institution and so for payment.</p> <p>A Technical and Financial Committee shortlists the projects before the investors gather again for the final decision.</p>

<p>Legal and administrative management</p>	<p>Very constraining and sometimes impossible for public agencies to delegate/transfer funds to private banks and vice versa.</p> <p>Public agencies can only spend budget on specific policy domains that have been assigned to them by the government. The Technical and Financial Committee of the FLAG is composed by the Agency of Biodiversity, the Office of Water, the Agency for Ecological Transition (ADEME) which can only bring technical and financial support to projects' activities related to their specific policy domains.</p>	<p>This option can be challenging <u>between cofinancers</u> as it requires more time for negotiations, writing and signing bilateral and multilateral agreements, integrating the participation of investors in their yearly budget.</p> <p>However, procedures are facilitated between the financers and the beneficiaries as only one grant agreement has to be established. This makes the process easier and more efficient.</p>	<p>This option is easier for cofinancers as it does not change their internal administrative procedures (due diligence checking, grant allocation). However, cofinancing adaptation is innovative, the mechanism remain a classic one.</p>
<p>Feedbacks from the experiment in Guadeloupe</p>	<p>Regarding the heaviness of legal procedures (pluriannual contracts between cofinancers and the independent entity), this option has not been chosen.</p>	<p>This option has been chosen by one public partner (Bank of Territories) who delegate 150 000 euros to the coordinating entity (ADEME). Despite the advantages of having one institution managing the funds, we can deplore some negative aspects : once transferred, the funds of the Bank of the Territories had to be considered under the ADEME's terms (restrictive rate of aid and policy domains) putting SMEs and associations in difficulty.</p>	<p>This option has been chosen by the majority of investors. Projects instruction is very slow, particularly in the public sector due to lack of engineering and heaviness of legal and administrative procedures.</p>

Further information

- [Video presentation of Guadeloupe demonstrator](#)
- [Explanation video of the Local Adaptation Fund](#)

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1.4 Insurance schemes in Europe

Covering damages

To accelerate investment in climate change adaptation, TransformAr is researching novel financing mechanisms. One of the influential financial instruments in adaptation finance is **insurance**. Therefore it is important to understand how far the insurance sector and insurance offers are prepared for and aligned to climate change and risks. In one of the TransformAr deliverables, the demos have **interviewed** experts from the **insurance sector** and **decision makers** responsible for or interested in the implementation of climate change adaptation measures to counteract natural disasters. By conducting these interviews, we try to understand the **current landscape of insurance offers** in the context of natural disasters and climate change based on a **gap analysis**. By comparing the results of the different demo regions we aim to improve the **exchange of ideas** and mechanisms across regions and sectors in Europe.

Key learnings

- We need to harmonize climate risk insurance in high-risk regions and for low-income communities
- There is an underpricing of climate risks due to old data use and lack of updated risk scenarios and the inability to deal with uncertainties
- Climate sensitive assessment models need to take on the challenge to continuously updated to the newest scientific insights to be used in investment portfolios
- By providing discounts or premium reductions we can promote incentives for risk reduction at the source, lessening the potential for future claims
- We need to tackle inconsistency in climate risk assessment and coordinate regulatory approaches at least in the EU.

Approach for understanding the role of insurance in climate change adaptation

Two approaches were pursued and combined in order to obtain a well-founded and representative picture of the significance of insurance in the context of climate change and to learn lessons from previous experience.

The first one is based on a **questionnaire** compiled in communication with the project partners in the demonstrators and partners experienced in empirical research. The questionnaire was structured along main topics, for example about the role of insurance in the context of climate change in general, the necessary data availability and measures proven to be beneficial to increase the insurance cover against natural disasters. The questionnaire was translated, where necessary, into local languages. To some part, the questionnaires were completed in the form of semi-structured interviews, while others were sent out and then completed by the respective experts and stakeholders. The interviewees were allowed to diverge to explore answers in more detail, when of interest and relevance for the goals of the interview. The later use of the results is in anonymized form, with no identification of the respondent or their organization beyond the sector and country of location. The total number of filled questionnaires is 14. However, the idea of this exercise is not to do empirical research, but to have the relevant information for the different regions in Europe, and in addition to have the view of the insurance sector.

The second approach is to **compare** the results from the interviews with related **literature** to assess the representativeness of the outcome and to ensure the correctness of the messages drawn.

The role of insurance in climate change adaptation

Climate change increases the risk of being affected by natural disasters such as storms, floods, droughts, heatwaves and forest fires. Even if the basic infrastructure is adapted to the new extremes, this will still take years and decades and may lag behind the extremes that then prevail. Figure 8 illustrates how the insured catastrophe losses increased since 1970. As a result, dealing with the consequences requires major financial efforts to **compensate for losses**, and in this context, insurance has attracted much attention lately as a tool in climate risk management. In addition to **financial compensation for losses** after an extreme weather event, insurance can provide **incentives to reduce risk**.

Figure 8. Increasing weather-related losses are reported by one of the world biggest re-insurance companies, [Swiss Re](#).

In fact, however, insurance cover varies from country to country in Europe, and in the event of natural disasters there is a more or less large **gap between insured and total losses**. For some years now, adapted insurance solutions to deal with the consequences of climate change have been the subject of intense debate at national and European level. For example, specific elements of insurance offers have been proposed in a [report](#) prepared in cooperation with the EU Commission. Another example is the European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority (EIOPA), which has developed a [dashboard](#) to present the drivers of a climate-related insurance protection gap in order to identify measures that will help in decreasing society's losses in the event of natural catastrophes.

The aim of this questionnaire is to take stock of how widespread promising approaches and existing procedures are implemented, to compare across regions and countries, and ultimately to identify a sustainable portfolio of suitable offers.

Earlier studies and experiences show that various measures have the potential to improve insurance cover. In the following, we will go through these by topic and find out whether stakeholders and decision makers are familiar with them and whether they are offered in specific regions.

Topics related to climate change and insurance

Topic 1: Access to climate hazard related insurance

Important is that insurance against natural disaster is available in a specific region. For floods, this is the case in most regions of Europe and also in six out of the seven demonstrator regions of the project. The exception is Guadeloupe, an overseas department and region of France in the Caribbean, where there is a lack of flood insurance related offers. In Finland, natural perils are part of a natural events insurance (NEI) bundling different perils in one insurance offer. In Norway, the Natural Damage Compensation Act (NDCA) covers most natural damage events. The NDCA is the law governing the administration of the Norwegian Natural Agency.

The same as for flood disasters, also storm insurance is available widespread in Europe and in all demonstrator regions with the exception of Guadeloupe. In Norway, it also covered by the NDCA and in Finland by the NEI.

Insurance against drought events is less wide-spread in Europe and not available, for example in Guadeloupe and Greece, and not common in Italy. In Norway, drought is not covered by the NDCA, but for agriculture, the government provides 70 % coverage for the loss of crops and production. For the remaining 30 %, additional insurance can be purchased. In Finland, it is part of the NEI.

Forest fire insurance is more common in southern countries of Europe such as in Spain, Italy and Greece. It is not available in Guadeloupe and not part of the NDCA in Norway. In Finland, it is part of the NEI.

Looking at other perils, in most countries of Europe, also insurance against hail is available or, as in the case of Finland, part of an insurance portfolio. In Norway, the NDCA in addition covers landslide and avalanche, storm surge, earthquake and volcanic eruption.

Topic 2: Insurance policies to increase natural disaster insurance coverage

More promising than individual offers and more convenient for customers is bundling of the relevant natural hazards, such as storms, floods and hail, into one insurance offer³. It is also advantageous to offer this insurance in conjunction with a frequently taken insurance, e.g. household contents insurance, mortgage contracts or fire insurance. Implementation of transparent and adaptive underwriting processes can consider changing climate conditions and continuously update risk assessments to reflect evolving climate scenarios.

In some countries of Europe, multiple extreme weather risks (floods, storms, hail, etc.) are combined in such a single insurance product. As outlined earlier, multi perils are for example bundled in one insurance offer in Finland, as it is also the case in Spain, Italy and Greece. “Natural Perils” is used as a combined term in most insurance products and is included in the NDCA coverage in Norway. In Guadeloupe, such offers are not available.

The purchase of extreme weather insurance connected to a far more common and enforced product (e.g. mortgage contracts, fire insurance) is not so common. However, in Finland, the NEI is connected to fire insurance. In Norway, for private citizens, the “Natural Perils” insurance (NDCA) is connected to the

³ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2018-04/insurance_adaptation_en.pdf

property fire insurance, and for public sector and businesses, it is usually connected to building insurance. Similar connections exist also in Greece and Spain, while they are not very widespread in other parts of Europe such as in Italy and Guadeloupe.

Another element to integrate climate change into the insurance offers is adaptative underwriting considering changing climate conditions. In most regions in Europe, it is not common and sometimes the concept is not understood. In other countries such as Finland, it is not yet ready at product level, but currently being developed and considered. For example, the areas of higher flood risk could change into higher risk areas for insurance.

Theme 3: Premium incentives and discounts

Further measures can lower the financial burden on customers. Financial discounts can be granted if the customer takes precautions to minimise the risk. Doing so the insurance industry also pushes investment into adaptation. Government subsidies can be granted for low-income households⁴. Compulsory insurance is being discussed in order to limit the individual financial burden by increasing the number of depositors⁵.

Looking at discount by insurers if the customer invests in precautional measures, this is seldomly the case. Example for such a tool is Finland, where for large companies pricing is partly based on risk management, e.g. fire risk and preparedness. Also, for flooded areas and preparedness, if the risk is elevated, the price may be higher. Such tools also exist in Norway, while they are not common or available in the other demonstrator regions.

Government insurance subsidies for low-income households seem not to exist on a larger scale. Although, in many countries in Europe, the state steps in with financial support in case of natural catastrophes. On the other hand, there is a push in most countries in Europe to underwrite private insurance. In summary, subsidies for low-income households are not common in Europe, also not in poorer regions such as in Guadeloupe.

Compulsory insurance against natural hazards is widely and also controversially discussed in Europe. It exists, for example, in Italy and Norway, where the natural damage insurance is mandatory in the sense that it is linked to all fire insurance on property. In most other regions in Europe, it is discussed but not implemented yet.

Theme 4: Community engagement and education

Other measures help to make the population aware of the increased risk of natural hazards. These include information campaigns related to climate change and natural hazards done by the private sector, e.g. the insurance industry, or by public bodies. Another factor to increase awareness is education, in schools and through training programmes, and further training, e.g. for authorities and companies⁶.

When asked whether being well informed about climate risks in general and how they will develop under climate change, this seems to be the case in most demonstrator regions, where the majority of people feel well informed about the consequences of climate change in their region. For example, in the case of Finland, forecasts and studies are well available and closely followed up. But exceptions exist, one being Guadeloupe, where a lack of information and subsequently awareness is reported.

⁴ <https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2022/11/03/with-climate-impacts-growing-insurance-companies-face-big-challenges/>

⁵ https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/ecb.policyoptions_EIOPA~c0adae58b7.en.pdf

⁶ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2018-04/insurance_adaptation_en.pdf

However, people in most demonstrators are not aware of private or public information campaigns related to climate and natural hazards and the role of insurance. Here, there seems to be a general lack and space for improvement.

Looking at education in school and professional education, climate change is indeed sometimes part of education in school, but it is often very theoretical, and the impacts are not clear for different sectors. In Norway, it is only offered in professional training for the insurance sector, but not part of general public education. In the other demonstrator regions, it is not lectured in school or not very prominently so that the interviewees are not aware of it.

Theme 5: Public-private partnership including information exchange

Key to increase the coverage and quality of insurance is a functioning public-private partnership⁷. This includes that governments and the insurance sector exchange data, set common objectives (e.g. what is the role of insurance in a climate change adaptation portfolio) and divide responsibilities (about the extent of private insurance and where the state may step in). Important is to promote the active and collaborative sharing of risk, hazard and impact data across stakeholders through the standardisation of metadata and the format of granular data that can be more efficiently and transparently shared across stakeholders. To this category belongs also the cooperation with scientific entities insuring that the knowledge about climate risks is state-of-the-art.

Public-private partnerships exist for example in Italy and in addition risk-sharing pools or schemes in UK, Norway, Spain, Italy and France. Their success is rated from being good in Italy to insufficient in other regions.

Theme 6: Catastrophe bonds and reinsurance

Another element to increase the economic and financial security in case of large events are supporting financial instruments such as pool-like structures (e.g. catastrophe bonds) and public reinsurance to transfer and share risks associated with extreme climate events⁸. This can be offered for specific temporary risks, such as frost and drought, or for goods or properties that are otherwise difficult to insure due to their location or other characteristics. The goal is to spread risk across a broader financial market to ensure the availability of funds for large-scale climate-related claims.

In Norway, for example, the NDCA is such a bond. The stakeholders in most other demonstrator regions are not aware of catastrophe bonds or comparable mechanisms. In the past, crop and flood damage has been compensated with state aid, however, this is not a regular measure.

Theme 7: Specific offers for cities and other sectors

Municipal insurance solutions are diverse and complex⁹. It includes to manage the risks of a city as such but also of almost all branches of municipal companies - for example in local public transport, administration, logistics, kindergartens, schools and hospitals as well as power plant projects and waste management. In view of a natural hazard it is recommended that cities assess their vulnerability, including for municipal infrastructure and extreme weather events, as well as reporting on how they use insurance as a mechanism for managing risks. This includes also promoting the active and collaborative sharing of risk, hazard and impact data across stakeholders through the standardisation of metadata. Another idea is that cities spread their risk by allowing cities to pool their insurance.

⁷ <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/financial-services/articles/insurance-companies-climate-change-risk.html>

⁸ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2018-04/insurance_adaptation_en.pdf

⁹ <https://www.amo.on.ca/sites/default/files/assets/DOCUMENTS/Joint%20and%20Several%20Liability%20Insurance/2023/TheFutureofMunicipalLiabilityandRiskManagementRPT2023-08-16.pdf>

In the agricultural sector, in contrast to only insuring the high-risk land, farmers should be compelled to insure all arable land as part of the terms and conditions of an insurance policy. Also beneficial is to link the access to wider agricultural sector subsidies (i.e. those relating to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) or those offered at national level) to the purchase of sufficient insurance protection in order to develop a tradition of being insured. Similar measures are conceivable also in other sectors such as forest and fishery.

In Finland, for cities, there is not a separate cover against natural phenomena, but it is part of the insurance of operations. In Norway, municipal buildings and some infrastructure is covered by insurance bought from an insurance company, and other infrastructure (e.g. roads) is covered by the NDCA.

In the case of Guadeloupe, there is the so called "l'Etat de Calamité Agricole" which could be translated into "Agricultural Disaster State". It aims to ensure that farms that have suffered crop or capital losses due to climatic events, and that meet the eligibility conditions, receive compensation financed by the National Fund for Agricultural Risk Management (FNGRA). It allows for compensation for a portion of the material damage considered "uninsurable", which is the direct result of exceptional climatic events. However, the process is administratively burdensome especially in overseas territories: There is a considerable lag between the time help is needed and when it is received due to the administrative process, which can be critical for matters such as plantation.

Theme 8: Other elements important to lower the risk

Other elements to lower the climate related risk are:

- Well-functioning early warning systems (including 4 main functions: early risk analysis, monitoring and warning; dissemination and communication; and a response capability),
- Real-time monitoring technologies to provide timely alerts and information to policyholders and stakeholders, allowing them to take preventive actions in the face of imminent climate risks,
- Technical emergency services such as the fire brigade and the health system should be equipped to deal with natural disasters, e.g. with heavy equipment for clearing roads, pumps for draining flooded cellars, aircraft for fighting fires and tents and medical equipment for accommodating evacuees, and
- In case of an event with problematic damages, important is an efficient and responsive claims processing to ensure timely assistance and delivery of funds.

When asked about how the people in the demonstrators rate the early warning system in their region, the answer is that the early warning system is in most cases well working but can be improved. In Guadeloupe, it is only effective for specific perils such as hurricanes and storms. For other weather risks, such as floods, the warning system is inadequate. The island has microclimates that impact certain regions more than others, even though the territory is small. This can significantly affect the agricultural sector. Also in other regions of Europe, people feel that the early warning is insufficient (Guadeloupe and Greece) or moderate (Italy and Finland), while the response is that they are good in Norway, where water levels in waterways and weather in general are closely monitored and warnings are issued through official channels.

Focusing on how well equipped the technical emergency services are in specific regions to fight natural disasters, there is a diverse picture for the preparedness of technical emergency services in Europe. In Guadeloupe, there is a clear lack of such equipment, the situation seems to be better in most other countries. In Finland, the rescue services have contingency plans and are well prepared, e.g. pumping water from the basements of houses, also information on where to get more equipment if needed. In other countries such as Norway, it depends on type and scope of the disaster. Small events are mainly handled sufficiently, but they will struggle with larger events.

In case of an event, it is important that the claims are processed swiftly and without too much administration. While the claims processing seems to be sufficiently fast and to the point in most regions, it is very slow in Guadeloupe and might vary according to the specific circumstances of the case and can be slow in specific cases.

In Finland, the activities of insurance companies are supervised by the Financial Supervisory Authority, which is attached to the Bank of Finland.

Discussion including the view of the insurance sector

This discussion is based on feedback from the insurance sector in terms of one of the biggest re-insurance companies worldwide, regional insurance experts and a company working as consultant for the insurance sector with a strong background in natural disaster related insurance.

They agree that insurance against natural perils is widely available in most parts of Europe and a common offer including storm, flood, hail and often also other perils such as forest fire, storm surges, land slides and hail. Insurance against **drought** is a new element and more and more often offered, for example for the agricultural sector, where also **freezing** could be a peril. Re-insurers offer multiple extreme weather risks (floods, storms, hail, etc.) combined in a single insurance product, where the purchase of extreme weather insurance is connected to far more common and enforced products (e.g. mortgage contracts, fire insurance), and adaptive underwriting considering changing climate conditions is gradually more often considered. Also, many insurance companies provide a **discount** if the customer **invests** in precautional measures, although this is often not known and not everywhere available in Europe. The insurance sector doesn't get government insurance subsidies for **low-income households**.

A measure discussed intensely in the insurance sector and also with decision makers is compulsory insurance, because the concern is that governments don't invest enough in awareness rising, precaution, adaptation and mitigation, and point at insurance as compensation. In some countries, though, compulsory insurance exists and is, for example, included in fire insurance.

When asking about the level of information about climate risks and related impacts, the answer is diverse and some insurers don't think that the available information is satisfying. However, the effort to have public information campaigns and climate impact and adaptation related projects and studies is seen and acknowledged. Examples are public initiatives such as the EU Copernicus climate service or the NatCat services of Munich Re or Swiss Re.

Public-private partnerships are promoted in many countries, for example risk-sharing pools or schemes in UK, Norway, Spain, Italy and France. In addition, when looking at insurance protection to larger population and government assets, products are often designed in partnership with local governments. However, their success is rated as being insufficient or moderately sufficient when looking at climate risks.

An emerging topic, in the view of the insurance sector, is sustainable insurance and responsible investment, indicating the willingness of the sector to support environmental protection, social equality and sustainable growth.

Conclusions and lessons learned

A key measure for integration of the insurance industry in climate change considerations, are **climate sensitive assessment models**. Insurers need to continuously update these models to reflect the latest scientific data and emerging risks, including changing rainfall patterns, rising sea levels, and increased temperatures. With sustainable investment strategies, insurers can contribute to climate change mitigation by integrating environmental, social, and governance criteria into their **investment portfolios**¹⁰. Another important element is collaboration and data sharing with governments and international bodies, as climate change is a global issue and science is ever further developing. In addition, **public-private partnerships** can help develop insurance schemes that provide coverage for vulnerable communities and sectors, ensuring that climate impacts are managed equitably.

Another effective measure is offering **incentives** for policymakers and decision makers to adopt climate-resilient practices. This includes provision of **discounts or premium reductions** for homeowners and businesses that implement precautionary measures, use energy-efficient technologies, or build according to green building standards¹¹. These incentives **promote risk reduction** at the source, thereby lessening the potential for future claims.

However, many obstacles to integration of climate risks exist. These are for example **coverage gaps in high-risk areas** and affordability and accessibility for **low-income communities**¹², as in Guadeloupe. As climate risks escalate, many insurers have either increased premiums significantly or stopped offering coverage in these areas altogether. As climate risks drive up insurance premiums, low-income households and marginalized communities are particularly affected. In many regions, these communities already face higher exposure to climate risks due to poor infrastructure and lower access to climate-resilient resources.

In Guadeloupe, for example, there is barely any insurance system to protect farmers from climate and natural risks. Private groups do not even offer insurance systems. Insurance against natural disasters and climate change is a significant issue in overseas territories, which are even more exposed to these risks. There is a push to **harmonize climate risk insurance in these regions**. A sense of unfairness surrounds the risk coefficient in the agricultural sector, especially in these territories, despite differences between them. The only existing system is inefficient and slow. For instance, after declaring a natural disaster, it took three months to assess the situation and estimate the loss, and up to 15 months for the administration to receive the forms, which does not align with the urgent needs of the agricultural sector. Furthermore, there is a need to **raise awareness, communicate, and accurately convey** the challenges of climate risk in the agricultural sector, emphasizing the necessity to create an appropriate insurance system.

A problem mentioned in the questionnaires is that climate change offers are not climate risk adaptive leading to an **underpricing of climate risks**¹³. Premiums are most often based on historical data that does not adequately reflect future risk scenarios. This is also related to **uncertainty** in climate projections. Although climate science has made significant advances, predicting specific weather events and their localized impacts remains **challenging**¹⁴. This is associated with coverage for slow-onset events, because most insurance policies are focused on acute disasters like storms, fires, and floods, but often fail to

¹⁰ <https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/de-de/wissen/publications/fa0b3cbd/the-role-of-insurance-in-a-changing-climate-what-next>

¹¹ <https://www.unepfi.org/forum-for-insurance-transition-to-net-zero/>

¹² <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/financial-services/articles/insurance-companies-climate-change-risk.html>

¹³ <https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2022/11/03/with-climate-impacts-growing-insurance-companies-face-big-challenges/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/>

address slow-onset climate events such as rising sea levels, desertification, or long-term drought, which can have in the long run devastating impacts¹⁵.

Also, other data gaps exist. This is a problem because accurate climate risk assessment requires comprehensive and up-to-date data beyond climate scenarios, such as precise elevation data, land use and assets, and most prominently critical infrastructure. The level of protection, for example by levees against floods, is only regionally available and there is no European wide cadaster.

There are still **insufficient incentives** for climate resilience. While some insurers have started offering premium reductions or discounts for policyholders who take steps to mitigate climate risks (e.g., fireproofing homes or installing flood defenses), these initiatives are still relatively limited, and the insurance industry has not fully developed the potential for incentivizing climate adaptation measures on a broader scale¹⁶.

Another gap is the not existing harmonization of rules and standards. Different countries and regions have **varying regulatory approaches**, leading to inconsistency in how climate risks are assessed, reported, and managed across markets. In some regions, regulatory frameworks are still in their infancy¹⁷.

As a result, significant obstacles remain, including uncertainty in climate projections, data gaps, affordability concerns, and regulatory challenges. Overcoming these hurdles will require concerted efforts from policy and decision makers, insurers, and international organizations to ensure that insurance schemes are not only financially viable but also effective in addressing the realities of a changing climate.

¹⁵ <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>

¹⁶ https://www.eiopa.europa.eu/publications/role-insurers-tackling-climate-change-challenges-and-opportunities_en

¹⁷ https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/ecb.policyoptions_EIOPA~c0adae58b7.en.pdf

Bibliography

- Bauer, A., Feichtinger, J., & Steurer, R. (2012). The Governance of Climate Change Adaptation in 10 OECD Countries: Challenges and Approaches. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 14(3), 279-304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2012.707406>
- Calliari, E., Castellari, S., Davis, M., Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Martin, J., Mysiak, J., Pastor, T., Ramieri, E., Scolobig, A., Sterk, M., Veerkamp, C., Wendling, L., & Zandersen, M. (2022). Building climate resilience through nature-based solutions in Europe: A review of enabling knowledge, finance and governance frameworks. *Climate Risk Management*, 37, 100450. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2022.100450>
- Climate Policy Initiative. (2023). *State and Trends in Climate Adaptation Finance 2024*.
- Davoudi, S., Crawford, J., & Mehmood, A. (2010). *Planning for Climate Change: Strategies for Mitigation and Adaptation for Spatial Planners* (Vol. 81). <https://doi.org/10.2307/41064641>
- Jørgensen, S., Termansen, M., & Pascual, U. (2020). Natural insurance as condition for market insurance: Climate change adaptation in agriculture. *Ecological Economics*, 169, 106489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106489>
- Marsalek, J., & Bernard, C. (2002). International Report: Stormwater management. *Water science and technology : a journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research*, 46, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2002.0657>
- Marsalek, J., & Chocat, B. (2002). International Report: Stormwater management. *Water Science & Technology*, pp. 1-17. Pauleit, S., Zölch, T., Hansen, R., Randrup, T. B., & Konijnendijk van den Bosch, C. (2017). Nature-Based Solutions and Climate Change – Four Shades of Green. In N. Kabisch, H. Korn, J. Stadler, & A. Bonn (Eds.), *Nature-Based Solutions to Climate Change Adaptation in Urban Areas: Linkages between Science, Policy and Practice* (pp. 29-49). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56091-5_3
- Termeer, C. J. A. M., Dewulf, A., Rijswick, H. F. M. W., Van Buuren, A., Huitema, D., Meijerink, S., Rayner, T., & Wiering, M. (2011). The regional governance of climate adaptation: A framework for developing legitimate, effective, and resilient governance arrangements. *Clim Law*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1163/CL-2011-032>
- Ščasný, M., Zvěřinová, I., Czajkowski, M., Kyselá, E., & Zagórska, K. (2017). Public acceptability of climate change mitigation policies: a discrete choice experiment. *Climate Policy*, pp. 111-130. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14693062.2016.1248888>
- United Nations. (2022). *Methodologies for assessing adaptation needs and their application*.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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